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JEM-Joining Educational Mathematics

Evaluation criteria for eContent quality

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¹ OJ L 79, 24.3.2005, p. 1.

Table of Contents

INTRODUCTION	4
GOALS OF THE QUALITY GUIDELINES	4
BLOOM’S TAXONOMY OF EDUCATIONAL OBJECTIVES	5
THE ARCS MODEL	6
EQUALITY OF LEARNING RESOURCES FOR MATHEMATICS.....	6
CONCLUSIONS	8
BIBLIOGRAPHY	8

The JEM Thematic Network aims to disseminate best practices in the use of web technologies for eContent in mathematics. To this end, the JEM portal provides a section in which Software and Services, Learning Resources and Use Cases can be published, rated, and reviewed by members of the JEM community. This deliverable describes the quality guidelines underlying the choices for the criteria selected in the review process.

Introduction

What is Quality eContent? André Weil, one of the greatest mathematicians of last century, gave an invited plenary address at the International Congress of Mathematicians in Helsinki in 1978. His answer to the question “What is good mathematics?” was that it is impossible to define what good mathematics is, but when a good mathematician sees good mathematics, he knows it.

In the same way it may be impossible to define in specific terms what good eContent is. We have, however, means to find out which content is good and which is not. Namely we simply follow the web logs, under the assumption that good content is content that gets used and referred to a lot. Rankings of search engines give also an idea of what good content is. These rankings make search engines valuable. So in a way, it may be even unnecessary to try to define what good eContent is. Search engines do that for us. This is actually what happened with formal reviewing established for traditional learning repositories: people do not use it, they actually check search engines, and possibly rankings based on top downloads, top favorites, etc.

Discussion about eQuality is ongoing on the JEM portal pages, both at the wiki and in the blogs. This document is a snapshot of the current position.

Goals of the quality guidelines

The JEM Quality Guidelines outlined in this report are meant to be used by e-authors who wish to submit sample best practice material to the JEM repository. These resources may eventually undergo a review process designed to identify best practices for online mathematics learning and teaching. The review process, based on these quality guidelines, will grade the quality of courseware published by the JEM network.

Rather than being quality evaluation criteria for generic content, the quality criteria described here have to be applicable to resources that consist exclusively of educational material covering studies in mathematics, statistics and application areas such as physics in school, college and university. A further requirement is the cross-cultural validity of the guidelines which need to be usable at European level. The JEM review process should take into account national quality certification if existent; however the final resources must have a broader appeal and be usable as reference for a wider European audience. These quality guidelines ought to reflect this requirement.

The pedagogical and technological criteria described in this document are designed so as to be used as basis for the compilation of the review form employed to rate the quality of JEM published resources. However, these criteria should also serve the wider audience when scoring a online resource and the authors when producing new electronic material.

Before attempting to give criteria for quality, one should reflect about learning objectives and what are the activities that the learning resources should promote.

Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives

According to Bloom (Bloom, 1956), one may classify a limited number of activities that affect the cognitive domain and involve knowledge and the development of intellectual skills. This domain is the one most relevant for the mathematics and scientific study areas since it includes the recall or recognition of specific facts (definitions and theorems abound in mathematics), procedural patterns (algorithms and solving strategies), and concepts that serve in the development of intellectual abilities and skills (abstraction).

There are six major competence categories, which are listed in order below, starting from the simplest behavior to the most complex. These categories can also be thought of as degrees of difficulties and may be used to classify learning objects. Notice that, if a learning module tackles more of them, then the first ones must be mastered before the next ones can take place. Each competence is described by the mathematics skills demonstrated by it and by some keywords that are likely to appear in the learning module.

Knowledge- Recall a definition or a theorem, basic knowledge of e.g. rules of derivation, trigonometric equivalences, terminology and major results in a certain area. Knowledge of values of constants like e . *Question Cues*: list, define, tell, describe, state, match, select, identify, show, label, collect, examine, tabulate, quote, name, what, etc.

Comprehension - Understand the meaning, translation, interpolation, and interpretation of instructions and problems. State a problem in one's own words. Understand a definition or a theorem and how they depend on other definitions, grasp the meaning of a certain symbolic expression, use abstract knowledge in concrete examples, derive and predict consequences of assumptions on mathematical objects e.g. given this function, describe its first and second derivative or write an algorithm to compute the greatest common divisor of two polynomials. *Question Cues*: summarize, describe, interpret, contrast, predict, associate, distinguish, estimate, differentiate, discuss, extend, give examples, give counter-example.

Application - Use a theorem or more theorems to show properties of a mathematical object. Describe a concrete example in abstract terms. Apply a solving strategy to solve an exercise in a new domain. *Questions Cues*: apply, demonstrate, calculate, complete, illustrate, show, solve, examine, modify, relate, change, classify, experiment, discover

Analysis - Separates definitions and axioms from theorems, understands logical structures of proofs and complex mathematical domains, recognizes hidden consequences following by initial assumptions and components of mathematical objects. Ability to classify abstract structures and objects, e.g. classify a conic. *Question Cues*: analyze, separate, order, explain, connect, classify, arrange, divide, compare, select, explain, infer

Synthesis - Define a new structure from known elements and derive its properties. Generalize a theorem or prove a new theorem. Relate the results in a certain area to

results in a different area. *Question Cues*: formulate, generalize, rewrite, combine, integrate, modify, rearrange, substitute, invent, what if?, compose

Evaluation - Compare and discriminate between ideas, assess value of theories, presentations and research. Be able to make hypotheses based on mathematical facts. Verify validity of mathematical claims. Judge usefulness of results. *Question Cues*: assess, decide, rank, grade, test, measure, recommend, convince, select, judge, explain, discriminate, support, conclude, compare, summarize

The ARCS Model

Best educational eContent will support synchronous and asynchronous online teaching so that it rivals and, in some respects surpasses, in quality, traditional contact instruction. The strength in virtual learning is that one may have direct contacts with students in a way which is not possible in a classroom. In online learning, one may trace the students' activities and spot their weak points thanks to extensive logs. One may also spot the weak points in instruction. If most of the students consistently fail to learn a certain method or result, the problem lies in the instructional methods chosen or in the supporting eContent or in both. In traditional learning, it is not possible to trace students' progress in the same way.

The following remarks apply to all learning in general. John Keller has formulated the ARCS model for quality eContent (Keller). The abbreviation is short for Attention, Relevance, Confidence, and Satisfaction.

The content must grab the students' attention immediately. This can be done by examples or by formulating an interesting question right in the beginning of the learning object. Also students' attention span is short. Ten minutes is a long time when listening to a lecture.

The content must be relevant to the student. That can usually be demonstrated by examples.

The content must engage students in active learning. In mathematics this means that students must actively solve problems as a routine part of any learning module. In that way students gain confidence that they have mastered the materials of the module.

Finally the learning objects must have a component with which the students can certify that they have mastered the materials. This will give satisfaction to the students.

The goals of the ARCS model can be realized in high quality eContent in a much more concrete way than in traditional contact instruction even though the same remarks apply also to contact instruction.

eQuality of Learning Resources for Mathematics

This section shortly analyzes some aspects of eQuality of learning resources for mathematics in order to relate this notion of quality to the reviewing process for eContent that is

published by JEM. The items in boldface refer to the criteria for which an evaluation is required by the JEM review form, as documented in (Olga Caprotti, 2007).

The most important characteristic is the academic and educational quality of the content as such. There should not be factual mistakes, and the narrations must be of high quality, references must be provided and clear attribution to creators of the assets is necessary. Educational quality can be measured if learning goals are specified and if there is feedback and assessment for students to check whether they have reached the goals. Pre-requisites are also fundamental in order to make sure that the background knowledge is covered. For mathematics instructions, a solid background is crucial for being able to grow in the kind of learning objective taxonomy mentioned before. **Accuracy of content, adherence to stated learning objectives, clarity of learning objectives, clear identification of target learners, professional presentation, credits to creators, feedback opportunity/assessment support, appropriate references, identification of pre-requisites**

Presentation of the content contributes to its quality by making safe design choices, conforming with accessibility guidelines and to good user interface. A learning resource should minimize the additional cognitive overload for students that are faced with a new technology by adopting a uniform design and user interface. The choice of a technology must be guided by the purpose of making learning more effective and engaging, this often means that clear instructions must accompany the asset in order to clarify its intended usage, what activities to carry out. **Ease of navigation/user interface, accessibility, clarity of usage instructions, appropriate use of technology, effective/engaging use of technology**

IPR should be respected and credit given to assets that are re-used (images, graphs, java applets, flash applets). Properly credited authors will share more if their work is recognized. **Credits to creators**

Technological quality can be rated in terms of the usability and portability of the resource. eContent is meant for use in various learning environments and on different devices: a personal computer, hand-held mobile devices such as new intelligent telephones, and portable players etc. The technological choices will limit the usability of the resource if not chosen carefully. A tightly printed lecture note used in the past is not suited for the small displays of telephones. **Technical requirements documentation, usability in learning environments**

Good eContent uses, as much as possible, open standards to ensure that the materials remain usable for a long time. What comes to mathematics, mathematical formulae should be encoded using semantic markup where possible, e.g. MathML and/or OpenMath, or a representation that preserves to some extent the mathematical meaning (TeX is better than an image). This will enable manipulation by computational software and conversion to less demanding representations (for instance for typesetting on a printer or in a browser) or to accessibility formats. **Usability in learning environments, metadata accuracy**

Finally, the feedback from other users is a good measure of quality. Case studies describing activities that have used successfully a certain resource with documented

results on the learning outcome of the students are an important factor. **Availability of case studies**

Conclusions

Good quality educational eContent should implement both Bloom's Taxonomy and Keller's ARCS model.

Good eContent is easy to use. Everything should work right away without the students having to install additional software.

Good eContent should also scale gracefully from large monitors and video projectors to hand-held devices. This sets requirements on the presentation, and demands new thinking in the creation of the content. Complicated arguments must be broken into parts that can be presented in few sentences.

To ensure longevity, quality eContent should use open standards whenever appropriate. Commercial systems, whose proprietary format exports to open standards, are often good choices for the production of the content.

Finally the factual representation of content must be correct, narrations of high quality, and references appropriate. In the past this has been checked by peer review. Today peer review has, to a certain extent, been replaced by a public review: content can easily be published, and the comments of the users may be the only review that one gets.

Traditional peer review process is too slow for the fast moving field like eLearning. What is good today may suddenly be obsolete tomorrow because of the changes in technology. The last word is in the hand of the users. Content, which gets used a lot and which is being referred to in many places, is usually good. Ranking is done by the search engines.

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